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MUSKETEER

**Machine Learning to Augment Shared Knowledge in
Federated Privacy-Preserving Scenarios (MUSKETEER)**

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**D8.3 Project communication and engagement
activities**

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Author(s):	Antoine Garnier (IDSA)
Participant(s):	ALL participants
Reviewer(s):	Stephanie Rossello (KUL), Lucrezia Morabito (COMAU)
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Contact:	Antoine Garnier – antoine.garnier@internationaldataspaces.org
Website:	www.MUSKETEER.eu

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Executive Summary

This document describes the communication and engagement activities and present the new supporting material of the MUSKETEER project. It provides an overview of the actions that have been undertaken during the first half of the project and those that are foreseen in the second half. It includes a review of the Key Performance Indicators, channel per channel, as described in the Description of Actions. The document eventually includes a specific section related to the COVID-19 situation, its impact on dissemination and the related envisioned mitigation solutions.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BDVA	Big Data Value Association
BDV PPP	Big Data Value Public-Private Partnership
CA	Consortium Agreement
COVID-19	Coronavirus Disease 2019
DoA	Description of Actions
EBDV	European Big Data Value (Forum)
EEN	European Enterprise Network
EFFRA	European Factories of the Future Research Association
ERRIN	European Regions R&I Network
EUM	End-User Management (Committee)
GA	Grant Agreement
IAIPRI	Impact Assessment Intellectual Property Rights and Innovation (Committee)
IDSAs	International Data Spaces Association
JRC	Journal Citation Reports
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
POM	Privacy Operations Modes
PPP	Public-Private Partnership
RIA	Research and Innovative Action
SME	Small & Medium Enterprise

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose

The deliverable 8.3 “Project communication and engagement activities” aims to describe the actions that have been undertaken midway through the project and report their status. It presents the work done and validates that the project communication activities are still aligned with key performance indicators envisioned in the Description of Actions. It also outlines the communication actions planned in the coming months. The document eventually gives a special attention to the evolving situation of COVID-19 and how to adapt our dissemination and communication activities to it.

1.2 Related Documents

The Communication and engagement activities deliverable is an important element of the WP8. It also has strong ties with different committees set up in the project whose discussions are described below.

Figure 1 Relationship of D8.3 and the rest of WP8 documents

As stated in the D8.2 “Dissemination and Communication Plan”, the deliverable D8.3 is **defined** by the directions envisioned in this plan. D8.3 applies the strategy arranged in the early stage of the project. It also **provides inputs** how to adapt for the rest of project and describe possible mitigation actions when needed. This document is also helping the preparation of the Evaluation and impact assessment (D8.6).

As mentioned, dissemination and communication actions are strongly related to the activities of different committees established in the project. D8.3 “Project communication and engagement activities” present a first report of these activities:

The Impact Assessment IPR and Innovation Committee (IAIPRI Committee) aims to take care of external request made to the consortium and concerning its activities. The MUSKETEER project has received some requests that have been discussed during each committee organized on the occasion of our General Assemblies. The IAIPRI Committee had 4 sessions along the 18 first months of the project. Dissemination opportunities but also information requests from various organizations have been received. Most of them have been accepted and dealt with, some have been postponed to a more mature state of the project (e.g. is the platform open? Can we test it?) and invited to stay informed using our social networks channels.

The End User Management Committee (EUM Committee) aims to coordinate end users and prepare the pilot scenarios before and during the validation phase. The work with this committee is out of the scope of this deliverable.

1.3 Document Structure

The document is divided in two main sections. The first one provides an update on the dissemination and communication strategy and the status of the different activities channel per channel but also a special focus on how to adapt to the new situation due to covid-19. The second section provides some figures about partners ‘dissemination activities (based on the tracking of each partner’s activities) and also a quick update on our internal organization with regard to the COVID-19 crisis.

2 Update on dissemination and communication strategy

2.1 Dissemination acceleration strategy

2.1.1 Specializing channels and cross-fertilization

As a RIA, the MUSKETEER project is producing a lot of high-level content (scientific papers, conference presentations, industrial organizations workgroups contributions) that has a great value for communication. Nevertheless, this content is highly specialized. In order to reach a relevant audience, we tried to specialize some of our communication channels. For instance, our LinkedIn group became our expert channel on Privacy Preserving Technologies while Twitter took the role of announcing relevant events and spreading the work about expert discussions happening in our LinkedIn group. This strategy was presented during our General Assembly in November 2019 in Dortmund and is now in place.

Social media

- 1 LinkedIn account | 1 post per week on average ; +200 followers
 - Week 27: 12 posts
 - 1 post per week is a lot, we don't lose followers, higher than Twitter (49)
 - Objectives
 - Create an expert community around PPTs with quality news and even talks between members
 - Draw attention to our project
 - Which information
 - Scientific paper, newspaper articles, original content from partners ☺: everything concerning PPTs
 - Status of the project: events, prototype release
- Actions
 - Reminder about LinkedIn strategy during next GA

Figure 2 Focusing LinkedIn group activity to become a reference expert group on PPTs

Whenever a highly specialized content is shared and available on our LinkedIn group, the information is also shared on Twitter in order to invite this audience to discover the content. We also tend to use more Twitter for events communication. Information concerning our

events can be found here (internal, external) but also events organized by the partners related to the project itself or to its topics (tweets and a majority of retweets).

It is also worth noticing that a large part of the technical and scientific content produced through the project is reused in our different channels. Presentation of scientific papers or recording of conferences can be found on our social networks, especially on LinkedIn.

Figure 3 Specialization and cross-utilization of content on LinkedIn and Twitter

2.1.2 Securing programs

During our General Assembly in November 2019, we presented the status of our dissemination and communication activities using the KPIs described in the DoA. Based on partners 'activities, we reported the progress on each task ensuring we're still aligned with them, not experiencing any delay. It has been the occasion to clarify some KPIs that could be understood broadly (such as Open Source community engagement). Finally, it enables us to discuss and agree on future tasks that were not started at the time (News release) and secure future actions. For instance, the prototype, expected for month 18, will be the occasion to communicate on MUSKETEER but also on its use cases. Schedule a program in advance helps us to ensure a smooth running of the work package, drawing a credible path to reach our KPIs.

2.2 Adapting to an evolving situation: COVID-19

COVID-19 surprised us at the end of February 2020 while preparing the last details for our first hackathon. We first decided to wait, then move it online, then postpone it (exact situation and

evolution described in section 2.5). For Dissemination and communication activities, such a situation means less occasions to talk about the project on one side and the shift of many items on other channels, especially digital ones. For instance, we planned to present our project during the Hannover Messe in April 2020 on the IDSA booth. Following IDSA's efforts to shift all their activities on a digital expo, the MUSKETEER project was included in their booth and also presented online.

Figure 4 Moving online with IDSA Virtual Expo in response to the COVID-19 crisis

On the long-term, we'll be participating to more online events, with the help of our partners, joining online workshops and group meetings to present the project. For other activities, that are not easily doable digitally we'll be postponing them (e.g. hackathon). This strategy does not put our KPIs at risk as we were already on a track before the crisis started and the postponed activities can still take place by the end of the year.

2.3 Channels

2.3.1 Partner's Networks

Partner's network refers to the organizations in which partners are directly represented (mostly on national and European levels).

Regarding **European Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs)**, we've been especially active with the BDVA Big Data Value PPP participating to different events organized by the network such as BDV PPP Summit in Riga last year, where MUSKETEER presented its manufacturing use case. We also participated in a Technical committee (Brussels, 2 Oct. 2019) and a Steering Committee (Brussels, 27 February 2019) or to the Best Success Story Contest organized by the network.

Figure 5 Presenting MUSKETEER at the BDV PPP Summit in Riga

More largely, we have been active with the BDVA and were involved in its main event, the EBDV Forum in Helsinki, of which MUSKETEER was a partner and where we presented a poster. We also introduced our project during an EFFRA event "Artificial Intelligence for Manufacturing".

Figure 6 Sponsoring EBDVForum, presenting at EFFRA “Artificial Intelligence for Manufacturing” event

Dissemination activities of our project in sectorial Initiatives include participation in events of the Hellenic Society of Orthopaedic Surgery and Traumatology (75th Congress) and the European Society of Radiology (ECR 2020, event shifted online due to Covid-19).

We have not been reaching out to **Established open networks** such as Enterprise Europe Network (EEN). The network is targeting SMEs and we will be contacting them later on in the project once we’ll have a more advanced prototype. For the same reason, we will be getting in touch with **Regional Entities** such as ERRIN (European Regions R&I Network) once the project will be able to present a prototype.

2.3.2 Events

The MUSKETEER project has been presented in a handful of events along the first 18 months of the project using the partners’ activities. In this section, we will proceed with a brief recap of various categories of events we joined to ensure we are reaching the objectives set in the Description of Actions (O3. Enhancement of the Data Economy). For the complete list of events the consortium attended in this first period of the project, please see Annex 1.

10+ industrial diffusion events In respect of their company agenda, all the partners attended events following the different fields of interest (security, big data, artificial intelligence, manufacturing, health) putting this KPI on a good track and making it already achieved. As an example, we would like to highlight the presentation of MUSKETEER made by Tree Technology during the Big Things Conference in Madrid. The yearly conference focus is on Data and AI. Our colleague Roberto Díaz hold a talk that provided the project with a technical presentation highlighting the objectives of MUSKETEER but also the challenges of Federated Machine Learning [1].

5 workshops First workshops have been organized in relationship with the project such as the one organized by KU Leven where first description of MUSKETEER have been shared and discussed in 2019 or lately with Imperial College Luis Munoz who participated into a webinar

for Ericsson with a presentation on “Federated Machine Learning under Attack” (April 2020). This KPI is on a good path even if it is worth noticing that we are still early in the project to discuss about the project in workshops (the first results are only now emerging).

3 workgroups attendance As mentioned above, MUSKETEER already had the chance to be presented and discussed in several occasions that led to different publications such as “Big Data challenges in Smart Manufacturing Industry (ed. 2019)”. This Discussion Paper on Digital Europe Big Data challenges for Smart Manufacturing Industry is an outcome of the Smart Manufacturing Industry group, in BDVA, co-lead by Engineering or on Privacy Preserving Technologies, again in the context of BDVA, with a position paper “Data Protection in the era of Artificial Intelligence” [2].

2.3.3 Social media

As mentioned above, and refining our strategy presented in D8.2, we have started to “specialize” our social networks channels to better organize the content we produce and the one shared by partners.

Our Twitter channel is responsible mainly to announce events in which we will be participating but also to document and highlight our actions once done. We are also directing Twitter users towards our LinkedIn group when presenting expert content.

We use our LinkedIn channel to publish content produced by us or others. In a near future, we will be also adding blog posts around Federated Learning and other technical activities from the project to facilitate the dissemination of technical concepts especially.

Figure 7 Expert content presented on our LinkedIn group

In regard to the KPI, we're following a continuous growth putting us on a good tack to reach the mark 200 followers on each channel (93 followers on Twitter and 74 on LinkedIn on month 16 of the project: April 2020). It is worth noticing that we expected an acceleration due to the organization of the hackathon in March 2020 but its postponement prevented it.

2.3.4 Media

Activities towards media have just started. As mentioned in the D8.2, we would like to use large media to present our use case in connection with the release of the first outcomes of the project. This activity is currently starting. We're contacting PR department of the consortium' partners to develop stories that could be presented to large media. In that direction, as mentioned above we participated in the Best Success Story Contest organized by the BDV PPP. In case of selection, the project will be presented largely, especially during the EBDV Forum, an event covered by local and specialized media. Our program regarding the KPI of 6 press releases (as mentioned in the DoA) would be to use the release of the first version of the prototype and to make 3 successive press release, one technical first to present the prototype itself and then 2 other in closer relationship with the use cases (Manufacturing and Health). This operation should be renewed with the final version of the prototype (3 PR: 1 technical, 1 tailored to the manufacturing use case, 1 tailored to the health sector).

2.3.5 Scientific publications

As a Research and Innovation Action, we have a continuous scientific activity along the project. The first period of the project has seen first submissions to scientific conferences and journals. Some of them have been already accepted such as "Defending against Poisoning Attacks in Online Learning Settings" from Imperial College. Several papers are currently in preparation, the rhythm of submission will intensify as the project progresses. It is also interesting to note that the level of competition has recently increased a lot in machine learning conferences driving down dramatically acceptance rates due to the actual interest of the field in the scientific community. Therefore, papers must be re-submitted as the time period for review and publication are longer now.

12 publications in conferences and 12 publications+ in JCR journals as defined in our KPIs list are taken care of by the research organizations members of the project but also some technical partners as IBM or Tree Technology. As said their activity will intensify thanks to the first results of the project.

2.4 Communication material

We have extended our communication material beyond the KPI presented in the Description of Actions. The DoA required for a brochure of the MUSKETEER project. We produced it as described in D8.2 and started its distribution. On the top that, we added a rollup that we used for the EDBV Forum and that we planned to use for the hackathon. This rollup contains a brief diagram presenting of our project but also its objectives.

Figure 8 MUSKETEER rollup

We also produced a short video for the project tailored for social networks (in its squared format) that is pinned at the top of our Twitter account. For the sake of convenience, we also uploaded it on YouTube [3].

Figure 9 Promotional video of MUSKETEER project

2.5 Hackathon

2.5.1 Overall objective

The organization of two hackathons have been defined in the KPIs list concerning the dissemination activities. This action enables to stress test the privacy and the security of the machine learning algorithms used in the platform as described in the Description of Actions. But instead of organizing a first large event using well-known tools such as Kaggle or others, we decided

to go for a smaller event open to a limited number of participants. The main reasons for this choice were the limited time we had to organize it considering that we wanted to have it in March but also the difficulties related to the MUSKETEER's client library that could represent a problem/barrier to host a competition on these platform. More information related to this point and other recommendations we elicited can be found in the preparation document available on Box where we considered the different options.

In this first hackathon we wanted to propose a challenge related to the security of federated learning algorithms to data poisoning, faulty and/or noisy users in the platform. Then, the participants would have to develop algorithms for robust aggregation of the information (gradients or model updates) sent by the users to the central node during the training of the model.

This challenge was opened to participants in three different locations in Berlin, Dublin and Palermo where teams mixing internal and external participants to the project should have joined for our hackathon.

2.5.2 Partnerships

Following first contacts with a Berlin-based company called Xain.io offering Federated Learning as a Service, it has been decided to join forces with them to organize this event. Therefore, Xain should have hosted the Berlin and main part of our event. Strongly engaged in the community around federated learning (the company founded the Meetup Federated Learning in Berlin), the partnership was of mutual benefit. On its side MUSKETEER project was bringing people with strong academic background but also the dissemination power of the consortium and its partners. The hackathon eventually turns to become a 2 days event with a meetup the day before on "Security aspects of Federated Learning algorithms" to introduce the hosts, the challenges and welcome the participants.

2.5.3 Communication activities

Different communication activities were envisioned. In preparation of the event, we set up an Eventbrite page but also a dedicated page for the meetup and use our social networks but also direct emails to announce and support the organization of the hackathon. Some commercial ads have been considered prior to the meeting especially on Xain side to promote the event on social networks mainly.

Figure 10 Registration platform for the hackathon

For the event, we produced t-shirts that should have been given to the participants as a modest award for their participation. The event did not include any monetary compensation. Xain also considered to produce more material with bags and lanyards as presented below.

Figure 11 branded material to share with the participants

We were also preparing live tweet session and activities on social networks with Xain. Finally, this event should have provided us with some content for blog articles.

2.5.4 Evolution following the Covid-19 crisis

At first, when the crisis started in Europe, it was decided to shift the event online, cancelling only the meetup. But after the first lockdowns measures were taken, it became more and more clear that we will have important difficulties to simply make the event happen. Finally, the hackathon was postponed entirely (including the meetup) until further notice. Its organization by the end of the year should be discussed again during our next General Assembly in May.

Figure 12 Postponing of the hackathon

3 Dissemination and Communication: internal organization

3.1 Tracking process

As explained in the deliverable 8.2 Dissemination and Communication Plan, we established a tool (Excel spreadsheet) to report the dissemination activities of each partner. A complete view can be found in Annex 1 gathering a detailed view of the various actions. In order to keep track of this work and in regard to the KPIs, the table below presents our achievements:

Table 1 Achievements in regard to the DoA KPIs

Activity	Targeted communities	KPIs (at least)	Responsible	M18
Scientific publications	Scientific/research community, industrial companies, SMEs	12 publications in JCR journals or conference	All; led by scientific partners.	6 submitted, 3 under review, 2 rejected, 1 accepted
Conference presentations	Scientific/research community, industrial companies, SMEs	12 participations. 12 publications	All; led by the project coordination	13 participations w/ publications
Workgroups	Industrial data providers and consumers	3 workgroup attendance	All; coordinated by tech	2 workgroup attendances

			development partners.	
OS community engagement	Open source community, software developers.	10 open source web communities interaction	All; coordinated by tech development partners.	GitHub OS releases, Meetup (postpone),
Hackathon	Open source community, software developers, hackers	2 Hackathons on Adversarial Attacks with at least 100 researcher participants	All; coordinated by tech development partners.	1 hackathon (postpone)
Training sessions	Technical and software community	5 sessions	All; coordinated by tech development partners.	During hackathon (postpone)
Leaflets, brochure, factsheet	General public, media institutions, industrial companies, SMEs, scientific and research community	1 brochure (created in the first 6 months) 1000 copies to be distributed.	All; coordinated by dissemination leader	Yes + rollup and video
News release	General public	3 news releases a year per country.	All; coordinated by dissemination leader	Just started
Social media	General public	1 Twitter account; 1 LinkedIn account; 1 post per week on average; +200 followers.	All; coordinated by dissemination leader	93 f. on Twitter and 74 f. on LinkedIn
Newsletters	General public	1 per year.	All; coordinated by dissemination leader	Through partners' activities
Website	General public, industrial data providers and data consumers,	3000 unique visitors	All; developed by project coordinator	Yes

3.2 Moving towards a more dematerialized process

3.2.1 Online General Assembly

Facing the impossibility of organizing a physical meeting in the new situation brought by the Covid-19 in Europe, we decided to organize our second General Assembly, online. Following the examples of numerous other EU projects that had to shift their internal meetings online, MUSKETEER project in turn decided to set up an online meeting in place of its General

Assembly intended to take place in Palermo with the support of Engineering. This new configuration pushed us to rethink the organization of such a meeting, taking into account its specific constraints. The first draft of the agenda is considering having the first day of the meeting dedicated to the report of the different activities (following the usual organization of our meetings). Unlike our previous General Assembly, the second day could be dedicated to specific meetings (technical, legal, use cases) gathering only the required audience and possibly done parallelly.

3.2.2 Review meeting

Our mid-review meeting is intended to take place on July 21, 2020. It will again happen online instead of being held physically. This meeting which aims to present the outcomes of the project after 18 months, will be prepared a week ahead using an online meeting tool instead of the day before like in a physical meeting. This presents the advantage of positioning a rehearsal presentation several days before the official review letting our consortium the time to discuss and smoothly adjust the presentation.

4 Conclusion

The dissemination and engagement activities of the MUSKETEER project are in a good progress on these first 18 months. Thanks to the first outcomes of the project to be published soon, our consortium will be able to communicate and disseminate its activities more broadly. The new period will see more scientific achievements but also technical material ready to be shared. We will also have to better integrate the new context resulting from the Covid-19 crisis that will most probably continue to impact our dissemination activities along the whole project duration.

5 References

- [1] <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Pjjd53MwLGA&feature=youtu.be>
- [2] <http://www.bdva.eu/downloads>
- [3] <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7vm5iqjob4k>

6 Annexes

6.1 Annex 1

Here is the aggregated information related to the dissemination and communication activities of the consortium:

PARTNER	MUSKETEER	TYPE	TITLE	ORGANIZER / PUBLISHER	DATE	PROJECT MONTH	COUNTRY	Link	NOTES/MOTIVATION/COMMENTS	STATUS
B3D		06. Event: Conference	ECR 2021	European Society of Radiology	01/03/2021	28	Austria	https://www.mysr.org/congress	B3D plan to exhibit at ECR2021, the major event of radiology in Europe and 2nd worldwide, to present its products and research projects to Radiologists from all over the world.	Planned
COMAU		04. Event: Workshops	Internal workshop for requirements definition	COMAU	03/04/2019	4	Italy		Contacts collected among Comau colleagues and suppliers (Automation system, robotics, Bosh)	Done
COMAU		02. Online: Website	Comau web page	COMAU	31/05/2019	6	Italy	https://www.comau.com/en/this-is-comau/innovationdigitaltransformation/research-and-innovation-projects		Done
COMAU		03. Online: Social Media	Musketeer project kick off	COMAU	06/01/2019	6	Italy			Done
COMAU		04. Event: Workshops	Mid term Musketeer project achievements	COMAU	01/05/2020	18	Italy			Planned
COMAU		06. Event: Conference	Participation on drafting of the Best Success Story for BDV	IDSA	30/04/2020	17				Done
ENG		06. Event: Conference	BDVA Activity Group	BDVA	26/02/2019	3	Belgium		Musketeer presented to all BDVA Activity Group participants	Done
ENG		06. Event: Conference	BDV Steering Committee	BDVe	27/02/2019	3	Belgium		Attendance of the BDV PPP Steering Committee meeting	Done
ENG		06. Event: Conference	BDV meet up	ALL	26-28/06/2019	7	Latvia	http://www.bdva.eu/node/12	BDV workshops with other projects under the PPP	Done
ENG		06. Event: Conference	Workshop on Artificial Intelligence for Manufacturing	EFFRA, BDVA, euRobotics	02/07/2019	8	Belgium	http://www.effra.eu/en/news/workshop-artificial-intelligence-for-manufacturing	Musketeer presented as project in AI for Manufacturing	Done
ENG		06. Event: Conference	Common European data spaces for Smart Manufacturing	EC	16/09/2019	10	Belgium	http://www.ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/common-european-data-spaces-for-smart-manufacturing	Musketeer promoted as project implementing a data/knowledge sharing platform	Done
ENG		06. Event: Conference	ICT proposers' day	ALL	19-20/9/19	10	Finland	https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/ict-proposers-day	Project dissemination in wide European forum	Done
ENG		06. Event: Conference	European BDV forum	ALL	14-16/10/2019	11	Finland	http://www.big-data-value.eu/eu-bdv-forum	Project dissemination in wide European forum, also required as we're part of the PPP	Done
ENG		06. Event: Conference	Project results contributing to data spaces for Smart Manufacturing	EC	22/10/2019	11	Belgium		Invitation to the interactive workshop to present the project view and how project results could contribute to setting up common European data spaces	Done
ENG		06. Event: Conference	Digitalization of Knowledge and Industrial Technologies	University of Bologna	7/11/19	12	Italy	http://eventi.unibo.it/dokit-2019/aggiornamenti	Knowledge Representation, AI and Industrial Exploitation	Done
ENG		06. Event: Conference	Contributing to the Best Success Story for BDV	IDSA	30/04/2020	17		http://www.big-data-value.eu/bdvppp-summit-2020/best-success-story/		Done
ENG		06. Event: Conference	BDVA Activity Group	BDVA	2/26/2019	3	Belgium		Musketeer presented to all BDVA Activity Group participants	Done
ENG		06. Event: Conference	BDV Steering Committee	BDVe	2/27/2019	3	Belgium		Attendance of the BDV PPP Steering Committee meeting	Done
ENG		03. Online: Social Media	Promotion through official ENG social media channels	ENG	2019		Worldwide	https://twitter.com/EngineeringSpa https://www.linkedin.com/company/engineering-spa/	linkedin posts, tweets and retweets	Done
ENG		03. Online: Social Media	Promotion through official ENG social media channels	ENG	2020		Worldwide	https://twitter.com/EngineeringSpa https://www.linkedin.com/company/engineering-spa/	linkedin posts, tweets and retweets	Planned
ENG		03. Online: Social Media	Promotion through official ENG social media channels	ENG	2021		Worldwide	https://twitter.com/EngineeringSpa https://www.linkedin.com/company/engineering-spa/	linkedin posts, tweets and retweets	Planned
ENG		06. Event: Conference	European Big Data Value Forum	BDVA	2-5/11/2020		Germany	https://www.european-big-data-value-forum.eu/	Project dissemination in wide European forum, also required as we're part of the PPP	Planned
ENG		10. Publications: White papers	Big Data challenges in Smart Manufacturing Industry (ed. 2019)	BDVA	2020			http://bdva.eu/	A Discussion Paper on Digital Europe Big Data challenges for Smart Manufacturing Industry. The Smart Manufacturing Industry group, in BDVA, is co-lead by ENG	Planned
ENG		09. Publications : Conference papers	TBD	ENG	2021					Planned
ENG		12. Publications : Article / Interview (press)	TBD	ENG	2020			https://www.ingenium-magazine.it/	1 article to be published in ENG magazine	Planned
ENG		12. Publications : Article / Interview (press)	TBD	ENG	2021			https://www.ingenium-magazine.it/	1 article to be published in ENG magazine	Planned
FCA		04. Event: Workshops	Internal workshop "as is analysis" and Musketeer objectives sharing	FCA ITEM	06/03/2019	4	ITALY			Done
FCA		04. Event: Workshops	Internal workshop Manufacturing Scenario : spot welding @ FCA plant	FCA ITEM	20/03/2019	4	ITALY			Done

FCA	04. Event: Workshops	Internal workshop Manufacturing Scenario : spot welding @ FCA plant	FCA ITEM	20/03/2019	4	ITALY			Done
FCA	03. Online: Social Media	Internal communication through Workplace by Facebook	FCA ITEM	07/06/2019	7	ITALY			Done
FCA	04. Event: Workshops	Technical contribution to "Best Success Story" contents definition for BDV	IDSA	30/04/2020	17				Done
IBM	04. Event: Workshops	AI Law & Ethics Conference	KU LEUVEN	28/02/2019	3	Belgium	https://www.law.kuleuven.be/citip/en/news/item/citip-conference-through-the-	MUSKETEER flyer was presented at the event	Done
IBM	06. Event: Conference	BDV meet up	ALL	26-28/06/2019	7	Latvia	http://www.bdva.eu/node/12	BDV workshops with other projects under the PPP	Done
IBM	06. Event: Conference	ICT proposers' day	ALL	19-20/9/19	10	Finalnd	https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-	Project dissemination in wide European forum	Done
IBM	06. Event: Conference	European BDV forum	ALL	14-16/10/2019	11	Finalnd	http://www.big-data-value.eu	Project dissemination in wide European forum, also required as we're par of the PPP	Done
IBM	04. Event: Workshops	Delivering Data Protection in Real Time Workshop	Oxford University / OASIS	09/09/2019		UK	https://privacyworkshop1	Project dissemination in wide Academic / Industry European forum for Privacy	Done
IBM	04. Event: Workshops	Theory and Practice of Differential Privacy (TPDP) at CCS 2019	ACM	11/11/2019	12	UK	https://ttdp.cse.buffalo.ec	Project dissemination in academic forum for differential privacy	Done
IBM	04. Event: Workshops	Privacy in Machine Learning (PriML) at NeurIPS 2019	NeurIPS	14/12/2019	13	Canada	https://priml-workshop.gi	Project dissemination in academic forum for machine learning with privacy	Done
IDSA	05. Event: Trade show, exhibitions	Hannover Messe	Hannover Messe	01-05/04/2019	4	Germany	s://www.hannovermesse.de/h	Exhibitor (presentation of MUSKETEER among IDSA activities)	Done
IDSA	06. Event: Conference	IDSA Summit	IDSA	25-26/06/2019	6	Germany	https://www.internationaldat	Annual presentation of IDSA activities	Done
IDSA	06. Event: Conference	High level event	IDSA	22/02/2019	2	Germany		Update on IDSA activities with national authorities	Done
IDSA	05. Event: Trade show, exhibitions	IOT Solutions World Congress	IOT Solutions World Congress	29-31/10/2019	10	Spain	ps://www.iotsworldcongress.c	Exhibitor (presentation of MUSKETEER among IDSA activities)	Done
IDSA	06. Event: Conference	2nd IDSA Winterdays	IDSA	3-5/12/2019	12	Tbd		Annual presentation of IDSA activities	Done
IDSA	05. Event: Trade show, exhibitions	Hannover Messe	Hannover Messe	01/04/2020	4	Germany	s://www.hannovermesse.de/h	Exhibitor (presentation of MUSKETEER among IDSA activities)	Rejected
IDSA	05. Event: Trade show, exhibitions	IDSA Virtual Expo	IDSA	20.04-15.05/04/2020	16	Online	ternationaldataspaces.org/ids	Exhibitor (presentation of MUSKETEER among IDSA activities)	Done
IMP	11. Publications: Scientific paper	Conference or Journal paper on Data Poisoning	S&P/CCS/PAMI/TIFS			NA		Paper to be submitted to a conference/journal. This paper will be an extension of the work submitted to ICML 2020 (Byzantine-Robust Federated Machine Learning through Adaptive Model Averaging). The timing to submit this paper depends on the acceptance of the conference paper.	Planned
IMP	09. Publications: Conference papers	Defending against Poisoning Attacks in Online Learning Settings	ESANN	24-26/04/2019	5	Belgium	https://www.elen.ucl.ac.be	Conference paper on data poisoning	Done
IMP	06. Event: Conference	IDSA Summit	IDSA	25-26/06/2019	7	Germany	https://www.international	Annual presentation of IDSA activities. We presented MUSKETEER project at this event	Done
IMP	02. Online: Website	RISS group Website	Imperial	01/02/2019	3	UK	http://rissgroup.org/	Describe MUSKETEER activities in our research group website at Imperial	Done
IMP	09. Publications: Conference papers	Byzantine-Robust Federated Machine Learning through Adaptive Model Averaging	AAAI	01/09/2019	10	US	https://aaai.org/Conferen	The paper was not accepted (possibly we did not target the right venue). We resubmitted to ICML 2020, one of the top conferences in machine learning. Arxiv preprint available at: https://arxiv.org/pdf/1909.05125.pdf	Rejected
IMP	09. Publications: Conference papers	Poisoning Attacks with Generative Adversarial Nets	ICLR 2020	25/09/2019	10	Ethiopia	https://iclr.cc/	Paper originally submitted to NeurIPS 2019 on 25/05/2019. The paper was not accepted, but has been revised and resubmitted to ICLR 2020. Paper currently under review. Conference to be celebrated in Ethiopia. (April 2020). ICLR is one of the top conference in machine learning. Arxiv preprint available at: https://arxiv.org/pdf/1906.07773.pdf . The paper was rejected despite we had a favourable opinion from the majority of the reviewers (we have resubmitted the paper to ICML conference)	Rejected
IMP	02. Online: Website	Personal website	Imperial	15/10/2019	11	UK	https://www.doc.ic.ac.uk/	Describe MUSKETEER activities in personal websites of Imperial's participants in MUSKETEER	Done
IMP	09. Publications: Conference papers	Byzantine-Robust Federated Machine	ICML 2020	07/02/2020	14	Austria	https://icml.cc	Paper originally submitted to AAAI 2020 on 5/9/2019. The paper was not	Planned

IMP	06. Event: Conference	Poisoning Attacks with Generative Adversarial Nets	ICML 2020	07/02/2020	14	Austria	https://icml.cc	Paper submitted to ICML, one of the top conferences in machine learning. Paper currently under review. Arxiv pre-print available at https://arxiv.org/pdf/1906.07773.pdf .	Planned
IMP	06. Event: Conference	Universal Adversarial Perturbations to Understand Robustness of Texture vs. Shape-biased Training	ECCV 2020	20/02/2020	14	UK	https://eccv2020.eu/	Paper to be submitted to ICML, one of the top conferences in machine learning. Arxiv pre-print available at https://arxiv.org/pdf/1911.10364.pdf .	Planned
IMP	06. Event: Conference	IDSIA Winterdays	IDSIA	3-5/12/2019	12	France	https://www.international	We presented MUSKETEER project at this event	Done
IMP	07. Event: Presentation / Lecture	Ericsson Webinar: "Federated Machine Learning under Attack"	Ericsson	08/04/2020	17	UK/Sweden	No website	Presentation of some of the work done in WP5 on the security aspects of federated learning, including the threat model released in deliverable D5.1	Done
KUL	11. Publications: Scientific paper	Federated Learning and GDPR -	KU LEUVEN	30/12/2020	24	N.A.	N.A.	Scientific publication on opportunities and challenges of federated learning	Planned
KUL	04. Event: Workshops	AI Law & Ethics Conference	KU LEUVEN	28/02/2019	3	Belgium	https://www.law.kuleuven.be/citip/en/news/item/citip-conference-through-the-	MUSKETEER flyer was presented at the event	Done
KUL	06. Event: Conference	9th Annual Data Protection and Privacy Conference	KU LEUVEN (participant)	20/03/2019	4	Belgium	https://eu-ems.com/summary	MUSKETEER project was informally discussed with some participants at the conference	Done
KUL	04. Event: Workshops	Towards Value Centric Big Data (E-Sides)	KU LEUVEN (participant)	02/04/2019	5	Belgium	https://www.evensi.be/centric-big-data-connect-people-	MUSKETEER project was informally discussed with some participants at the workshop	Done
KUL	06. Event: Conference	30 Years CITIP	KU LEUVEN	04/10/2019	10	Belgium	https://www.law.kuleuven.be/citip/en/citip-	MUSKETEER poster was presented	Done
KUL	04. Event: Workshops	AI Law & Ethics Conference	KU LEUVEN	18/02/2020	13	Belgium	https://www.law.kuleuven.be/citip/en/citip-	MUSKETEER flyer and logo were presented at the event	Done
KUL	10. Publications: White papers	White paper on policy recommendations for the legal	KU LEUVEN	30/11/2021	36	N.A.	N.A.	Dissemination of main (legal and ethical) project findings discussed in deliverable 2.6	Planned
KUL	12. Publications: Article / Interview (press, or	CITIP blog	KU LEUVEN	31/12/2020; 30/11/2021	25, 36	N.A.	https://www.law.kuleuven.be/citip/blog/	Vulgarization of main (legal and ethical) project findings via a blogpost on CITIP's blog	Planned
TREE	02. Online: Website	Promotion in TREE website	TREE	January 2019	1	Worldwide	http://www.treetk.com/en/R&D	Musketeer	Done
TREE	07. Event: Presentation / Lecture	Coffee and Learn. Success case	TREE	01/02/2019	3	Spain			Done
TREE	05. Event: Trade show, exhibitions	Participation with stand in Digital Enterprise show. MUSKETEER dissemination and communication to broad public	DES	21,22,23 May	6	Europe	https://www.des-madrid.com/		Done
TREE	07. Event: Presentation / Lecture	Presentation federated Machine Learning (MUSKETEER)	TREE / IDIAGORAS	01/06/2019	7	Spain	youtube.com/watch?v=Lkh5MQZfqc&t=3022s		Done
TREE	07. Event: Presentation / Lecture	Representing MUSKETEER in EBDVF Helsinki 2019	BDVA	01/10/2019	11	Finland	www.european-big-data-value-forum.eu/		Done
TREE	10. Publications: White papers	Contribution to whitepaper "Trends, existing solutions and recommendations for privacy-preserving technologies"	BDVA	July-October 2019	9,10,11,12	Europe		0in%20the%20era%20of%20big%20data%20for%20artificial%20intelligence_BDVA_FINAL.pdf	Done
TREE	07. Event: Presentation / Lecture	Coffee and Learn. Success case MUSKETEER. Machine Learning algorithms and POMs 1, 2, 3	TREE	01/10/2019	12	Spain			Done
TREE	07. Event: Presentation / Lecture	Presentation in Big Things 2019	BIG THINGS	01/11/2019	13	Worldwide	https://www.bigthingsconference.com/ https://www.youtube.com/w		Done
TREE	08. Event: Hackathon	Hackaton on ML attacks	TREE	Postponed due to COVID19	25-36	Germany			Planned
TREE	03. Online: Social Media	Promotion through TREE TW account	TREE	11/07/1905	1 to 12	Worldwide	https://twitter.com/tree_RD		Done
TREE	03. Online: Social Media	Promotion through TREE TW account	TREE	12/07/1905	13 to 24	Worldwide	https://twitter.com/tree_RD		Done
TREE	03. Online: Social Media	Promotion through TREE TW account	TREE	13/07/1905	25 to 36	Worldwide			Planned
TREE	02. Online: Website	Generation of a post in TREE forum	TREE		13-24	Spain			Planned
TREE	12. Publications: Article / Interview (press, or	Generation of project brochure	TREE	January 2019	1	Worldwide			Planned

TREE	12. Publications: Article / Interview (press, ot	Printing and distribution of project brochure	TREE	01/05/2019	6	Europe			Planned
UC3M	11. Publications: Scientific paper	Submission to PR/TNNLS/JMLR/NC	UC3M			-		Research results	Planned
UC3M	11. Publications: Scientific paper	Submission to PR/TNNLS/JMLR/NC	UC3M			-		Research results	Planned
UC3M	11. Publications: Scientific paper	Submission to PR/TNNLS/JMLR/NC	UC3M			-		Research results	Planned
UC3M	01. Online: Newsletter, email	Note on UC3M Newsletter	UC3M		10	Spain	http://newsletter.uc3m.es/	Informative note about the goals and basic achievements of the project, to be	Planned
UC3M	06. Event: Conference	Submission to ICML 2020	UC3M	13-18/07/2020	19	Austria	https://icml.cc/Conferences/2020/	Preliminary research results	Planned
UC3M	06. Event: Conference	Submission to ECML 2020	UC3M	not available yet	-	Belgium	not available yet	Preliminary research results	Planned
UC3M	06. Event: Conference	Submission to NeurIPS 2020	UC3M	not available yet	-	Canada	not available yet	Preliminary research results	Planned
UC3M	09. Publications: Conference papers	International Workshop on Federated Learning for User Privacy and Data Confidentiality	FL-ICML 2020	17/07/2020	20	Europe	http://federated-learning.org/	Paper submission	Planned